

IMPACT OF LAND USE/LAND COVER CHANGES ON GROUNDWATER LEVEL USING REMOTE SENSING AND GIS: A CASE STUDY IN RAJSHAHI DISTRICT

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Abstract

One of the most serious anthropogenic changes to the environment is urbanization. In the past few decades, there has been significant concern about how urbanization is affecting groundwater. Moreover, urbanization is increasing impervious areas causing less infiltration, which thus has an imperative impact on groundwater storage. Therefore, this study seeks to understand the influence of changes in land use and land cover (LULC) from 2002 to 2022 on groundwater levels in the Rajshahi area. Utilizing Geographical Information System (GIS) and statistical tests, a thorough analysis of long-term groundwater trends and spatiotemporal variations was conducted using data collected from 9 observation wells over a 20-year period. The findings point to an 89.5% increase in impervious built-up areas and a 29% reduction in vegetated land cover. On the other hand, Maan Kendall Test indicates that 55.55% have a strong inverse correlation with vegetation and 44.44% have a strong correlation with urban areas. That means as the rate of vegetation decreases, the groundwater level is declining day by day. In the same way, the built-up area prevents infiltration and also affects groundwater level significantly. These results underscore the crucial impact of both reduced vegetation and increased urbanization on declining groundwater levels in the northwestern region of Bangladesh as well as it will be further helpful for concerned authorities to take relevant actions.

Keywords

Groundwater; LULC; Built-up Area; Vegetation; Urbanization

1. Introduction

Urbanization is considered as one of the most serious environmental changes through worldwide. [1]. In the past few decades, there has been significant concern about how urbanization is affecting groundwater. Besides, due to urbanization, the impervious areas including roads and buildings are increased that reduce the infiltration rate into the ground. This decrease in infiltration has a substantial impact on groundwater storage, contributing to the depletion of groundwater levels [2]. The impact of land use change on groundwater recharge has been the focus of researchers worldwide. However, there has been minimal study conducted on this issue within the context of Bangladesh. In Bangladesh, groundwater serves as the main and frequently the sole reliable source of drinking, industrial, and agricultural water [3]. In this context, the study aims to ascertain how changes in land use and land cover (LULC) between 2002 and 2022 affected the groundwater table [4] in the Rajshahi area.

2. Methodology

This paper evaluates the effect of land-use and land-cover change on groundwater levels. Static water level data from a period of 2002 to 2022 for nine monitoring wells in the district of Rajshahi were collected from BWDB. Satellite images from LANDSAT-7 and LANDSAT-8 for the same years were also used. These data were used to prepare maps of the groundwater conditions and their variations in depth in different parts of the district. In this research, the maps were prepared using ArcGIS 10.8, which showed the study area, groundwater levels, and groundwater contours. Based on the analyzed collected data, several graphs were prepared in order to look into trends with regards to groundwater and the causes of depletion. An unsupervised classification method was used for image classification and post-classification techniques for LULC change detection [4]. It identifies four

categories of land use. These are waterbody, vegetation, bare soil & urban area. The accuracy assessment of LULC was evaluated using a confusion matrix and ground truthing. Spatial groundwater table maps created using groundwater data were associated with the obtained land use and land cover maps [4].

Geographical Information System (GIS) and statistical tests are used to analyze the long-term trend detection and spatiotemporal variation of groundwater levels [5]. Statistical tests like the Mann–Kendall test and Sen’s slope estimator were conducted to predict the trend variation of groundwater levels [5]. Lastly, Sen’s slope method was applied in this study to identify trend line slopes based on the rate of water level decline [5].

2.1 Study Area

Rajshahi District is situated in Bangladesh's Rajshahi Division which has an area of 2,425.37 square kilometers. Geographically, it borders Naogaon to the north, West Bengal (India) to the east, Kushtia and the Padma River to the south, and Nawabganj to the west. It is located between 24°07' and 24°43' N latitude and 88°17' and 88°58' E longitude. The area is well known for having a semi-arid and dry climate. With summer temperatures reaching up to 38°C, it is among the hottest places in Bangladesh. In contrast, the temperature in the winter is around 6°C producing an abrupt shift between the seasons. The annual rainfall of the area is about 1,200 mm and most of it

Fig 1: Study Area Map of Rajshahi District

falling during the monsoon. (Banglapedia, 2023).

2.2 Data Collection

This study uses static water level data from 9 groundwater table monitoring wells of the Bangladesh Water Development Board (BWDB). Data on static water levels were gathered from the wells shown on the map in [Fig 2].

The Enhanced Thematic Mapper Plus (ETM_p) Landsat 7 images for the years 2002 and 2012, along with the Thermal Infrared Sensor (TIRS) and Operational Land Imager (OLI) images for 2022 with a spatial resolution of 30 by 30 meters, were downloaded from the USGS Earth Explorer website (<https://earthexplorer.usgs.gov/>). The satellite imagery's general properties are listed in [Table 1].

Fig 2: BWDB Groundwater monitoring wells

Table 1: List of selected Landsat 7 and Landsat 8 scene information.

Respective Year	Season	Sensor	Resolution	Cloud Cover
2002	Summer	ETM β	30m	< 15%
2012	Summer	ETM β		
2022	Summer	OLI		

3. Results and Discussions

[Fig 3] provides a detailed visualization of the land use and land cover (LULC) transformation between 2002 and 2022, emphasizing significant shifts in urbanization and vegetation. Over the two decades, urban areas expanded dramatically, growing from 162.90 km² in 2002 to 319.06 km² in 2022, indicating rapid urban sprawl. This increase in urbanization was accompanied by a noticeable reduction in agricultural land, which experienced a net loss of 29%, decreasing from 1521.49 km² to 1080.32 km². The conversion of agricultural land to urban areas signifies a shift in land use priorities, likely influenced by population growth and economic development.

Figure 3: Decadal Change of Land Use Land Cover in Rajshahi District

A downward tendency in the pre-monsoon depth of groundwater has been observed over time. The image illustrates the declining pre-monsoon groundwater depth (GWD) in an area over time, as depicted by the maps for the years 2002, 2012, and 2022 [Fig 4]. The rate at which the groundwater level is dropped is shown in [Table 2].

Figure 4: Groundwater depth contours for 2002,2010 & 2022 in Rajshahi District

Table 2: Area Under Different Depths to Water Table

Year	2002	2012	2022
GWD	Area (%)	Area (%)	Area (%)
20-28	13.77	4	1.9
29-37	41.57	11	25.36
38-45	32.93	36	22.2
46-53	5.88	22	14.84
54<	5.8	27	35.7

GWD: Groundwater Depth

In the year 2002, the area of shallow groundwater depth was 20-28 meters with an area of 13.77%, which dramatically dropped to 4% in 2012 and further down to 1.9% in 2022. contrarily, the areas with a groundwater level deeper than 54 meters have also increased significantly from 5.8% in the year 2002 to 35.7% in 2022, which indicates that the groundwater depth shows a severe downward trend. This shall vary from the 38-45 meters that covered 32.93% in 2002, increasing to 36% in 2012, then slowly decreasing to 22.2% in 2022. This shows a downward shift, which simply exhibits increased vulnerability to lack of groundwater, majorly posing great agricultural and management risks to water resources.

The following figure represents the Maan Kendall's Tau Test for groundwater depth [Fig 5]. Here 6 out of 9 wells follow an upward trend, which means the water level is declining gradually.

Figure 5: Trend Analysis for Ground Water dept in different wells.

The Mann-Kendall Tau Test results for groundwater depth from nine monitoring wells in Rajshahi, Bangladesh, over 20 years (2002–2022) show significant trends. An upward trend in water depth at six stations: Paba, Borail, Matikata, Poromanondopur, Kamarga, and Godagari wells indicates a declining trend in groundwater levels. Moreover, there is continuous depletion in Paba and Borail, as indicated by their steady increases. In contrast, the water level fluctuations witnessed in the Konbaria and Deluabari monitoring wells have been comparatively smaller. In a nutshell, these results indicate the regional variations in groundwater patterns and pose major concerns regarding the long-term viability of these essential water sources in that region.

Table 3: Correlation Between Observation Well and LULC

Observation Well	Vegetation	Urban Area
Paba	-.659	.576
Borail, Mohonpur	-.998	.99
Deluabari, Durgapur	-.570	.653
Puthia	.608	-.522
Matikata, Mohonpur	-.980	.996
Poromanondopur, Godagari	-.566	.477
Arani, Bagha	-.968	.936
Kamarga, Tanore	-.968	.936
Konbaria, Baghmara	-.933	.890

The above table represents the correlation between observation well and groundwater [Table 3]. Significant inverse correlations with the amount of vegetation are seen in five out of nine observation wells. Consequently, research suggests that groundwater levels decrease in accordance with a decrease in vegetation. This implies that less vegetation limits the natural absorption & infiltration of water into the soil, leading to groundwater depletion.

Furthermore, four wells demonstrate a significant correlation with urban areas, where built-up regions inhibit infiltration, thereby impeding groundwater recharge. Urban expansion exacerbates the reduction in groundwater levels, as impermeable surfaces prevent effective water percolation. The results emphasize the mutual impact of urbanization and vegetation loss on groundwater dynamics, highlighting the necessity of sustainable land-use management in preventing groundwater depletion.

4. Conclusion

The result shows that land use land cover change has a robust impact on groundwater level. Out of 9 wells, 5 have a strong inverse correlation with vegetation and 4 have a strong correlation with urban areas. That means as the rate of vegetation decreases, the groundwater level is declining day by day. In the same way, the built-up area prevents infiltration and also affects groundwater level significantly. The authors also provide some recommendations:

- Rajshahi WASA should reduce dependency on groundwater by constructing a surface water treatment plant.
- It's essential to protect surface water bodies (e.g. ponds, canals, etc.) to reduce dependency on groundwater for irrigation in the dry season.
- Provision for reducing impervious surfaces in urban areas which prevents rainwater ground infiltration.
- Strict implementation of 'BNBC 2020' for regulations and restriction of land use changes that may impact groundwater levels.

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